

in these areas is not catching on because of the costs of transplanting and irrigating. An early-maturing rice variety khat could be direct seeded and grown with limited irrigation is desirable.

We evaluated the performance of 11 early-maturing rice varieties under direct seeding with limited irrigation in Ziauddinpur floodplain. The trial was in a randomized block design with three replications. Soil was sandy loam with medium fertility. Seeds at 80 kg/ha were sown 10 May 1985 in rows 15 cm apart. Fertilizer at 80-17.5-20 kg NPK/ha was applied. One presowing irrigation and two irrigations during the dry spell were given. The crop received 64 mm rainfall in 7 d in May, 222 mm in 18 d in Jun, and 387 mm in 23 d in Jul.

Pusa 2-21 and Hathi Jhulan failed because of a severe attack of brown leaf spot disease. Varieties ES1-1-1,

Plant height, days to heading, grain yield, and yield attributes of 9 direct-seeded varieties, Bihar, India, summer 1985.

Variety	Plant ht (cm)	Days to 50% heading	Panicles/m ²	Panicle length (cm)	Total spikelets/panicle	Filled spikelets/panicle	1000-grain wt (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)
IET6148	85.2	98	129	18.4	64.3	47.0	21.6	0.9
ES1-1-1	86.0	66	122	14.4	68.2	58.5	18.7	1.2
ES1-2-3	78.7	66	144	15.1	66.1	56.5	18.2	1.5
IET7617	82.2	91	127	18.4	63.0	46.1	21.3	0.9
IET7564	96.2	66	135	21.3	118.3	100.3	20.0	2.1
IET7613	91.3	92	124	18.9	65.8	48.6	22.0	0.8
ES21-2-1	81.2	85	116	14.5	65.7	51.3	19.0	1.0
Cauvery	84.3	86	117	18.8	74.2	54.6	20.9	1.0
Pusa 33	88.3	98	114	18.1	74.9	56.3	21.4	1.1
CD (0.05)	6.7		14	1.4	6.9	6.0	1.0	0.6

ES1-2-3, and IET7564 were the earliest to reach 50% heading, 66 d after sowing (see table). Heading time in general was 15-20 d longer than in wet season, perhaps because of soil moisture stress during early crop stages.

IET7564 had significantly higher

grain yield because it had more panicles/m² and filled spikelets/panicle. This semitall variety develops sufficient foliage in early stages to smother weeds. It has good grain quality and matures within 90 d, for harvest before floods in early Aug. □

Evapotranspiration rates of Jaya and Triveni varieties

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We studied evapotranspiration (ET) of Jaya (120 d) and Triveni (105 d) based on data collected 1978-85 at RARS, Pattambi (10°48'N, 76°12'E). ET was measured using two sets of volumetric lysimeters, and potential ET (PET) was computed using the Blaney-Criddle formula as modified by Doorenbos and Pruitt. Soil was lateritic sandy loam.

The varieties were not observed simultaneously, but were compared on the basis of daily mean ET in relation to

Table 2. Growth parameters of Triveni and Jaya, Kerala, India, 1986 kharif.

	Leaf area index	Leaf width (mm)	Leaf angle ^a
	<i>70 d after sowing^b</i>		
Jaya	4.0 ^d	8.0 ^e	170 ^{od}
Triveni	6.3	7.5	18°
	<i>Flowering phase^c</i>		
Jaya	4.2 ^e	8.9 ^d	16 ^{od}
Triveni	4.7	7.7	18°

^a70 d after sowing and 10 d after flowering.

^bTriveni and Jaya were sown on the same day.

^cAv of 3 stages; 1 wk before flowering, at flowering, and 10 d after flowering. ^dSignificant at the 1% level. ^eNot significant.

Table 1. Varietal variation in ET rates in relation to average PET. Kerala, India, 1986 kharif and rabi.

Variety	Kharif			Rabi		
	ET (mm/d)	PET (mm/d)	Percent increase of ET over PET	ET (mm/d)	PET (mm/d)	Percent increase of ET over PET
Jaya ^a	4.95	3.51	41	6.05	4.15	46
Triveni ^b	4.90	3.47	41	6.19	3.93	58
Difference in ET rates in relation to av PET	+0.05			-0.14		

^aAv of 3 seasons for kharif and 2 for rabi. ^bAv of 5 seasons each for kharif and rabi.

average evaporative demand of the atmosphere.

ET of Jaya was 41% higher than PET in Jun-Sep (kharif) and 46% higher in Oct-Jan (rabi). ET of Triveni was 41% higher than PET in Jun-Sep and 58% higher in Oct-Jan (Table 1). Jaya and Triveni had similar ET during kharif, but Triveni used 0.14 mm/d more water than Jaya during rabi. The higher ET of Triveni during rabi may have been because it had higher leaf area index and leaf angle and smaller leaf width than Jaya (Table 2). □

Rice grain dormancy and its alleviation

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Seeds of IR8, Jaya, PR106, PR4141, Basmati 370, and Punjab Basmati I were collected immediately after harvest, dried to 12% moisture, and kept under ambient conditions in cloth bags. We began germination tests immediately after harvest, then every 7 d until seeds